

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 12.10.2017 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Dr. Ravi Bhaskar	Chairman
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Dr. Sukesh	Member
4. Dr. Pavanchand Attavar	Member
5. Dr. Vishrutha K V	Member
6. Ms. Haritha Chandran	Member
7. Mr. Binoy K Kuriakose	Member
8. Mr. Anson Jose	Member
9. Ms. Alphonsa	Member
10. Dr. Sathyajith Karanth	Member
11. Dr. Vishnu Prabhu	Member
12. Mrs. Anitha D'Souza	Member
13. Ms. Laveena D'Souza	Member
14. Dr. Ravindran	Member
15. Ms. Swathi	External Member
16. Mr. Devaseelan S	External Member

Leave of Absence:

Leave of Absence was granted to the following members by the Chairman of Board of Studies:

1. Dr. Pavanchand Attavar (Member)
2. Mrs. Shwetha B (Member)

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 08.04.2017
2. Approve the Finalized Updated order of Credit Scheme for 2018-19.
3. Change of Syllabus from Annual to Semester Pattern of all Allied Health Courses.
4. Duration of Program Period.
5. Changes in Examination pattern.
6. Commencement of New Courses under B.Sc. and Diploma.

Chairman Dr. Ravi Bhaskar welcomed all the Board Members, who were present for the meeting. The meeting there after deliberated on agenda, as had been approved by the Chairman.

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 08.03.2017. As per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: The updated order of Credit Scheme as already approved for Academic Session 2018-19 to be implemented and changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 3: Discussion were made regarding the Syllabus to be changed from Annual to Semester Pattern of Courses of Allied Health Sciences. To change the Courses all AHS from annual pattern to Semester pattern was unanimously suggested by the committee members so as the students can be continuously engaged throughout the academic year and frequent evaluations can be done periodically to improve the quality of delivery of the curriculum and to enhance the skills of students. It was finalized and approved by the BOS.

Agenda No. 4: The duration of the program period was suggested to be changed to 3 years with six months of Internship by the members of BOS. It was finalized and approved by the BOS as per the suggestions given by the members of BOS.

Agenda No. 5: Changes in Examination Pattern was suggested by various Members of BOS, and scheme for End semester examination was updated as per the suggestions as follows:

- Scheme for end-semester examination:
 - ❖ Short Essay (No. of question: 5 Out of 7, Marks distribution: 05)
 - ❖ Short Answers (No. of question: 5 Out of 7, Marks distribution: 03)
 - ❖ To the point answers (No. of question: 5 Out of 5, Marks distribution: 02)

The decisions were made and approved by the BOS as per the suggestions given.

Agenda No. 6: Further suggestions were made regarding the addition of New Courses by the Various Members of BOS, as the Courses are high in demand and only Few Colleges are offering the Course. Keeping in mind to cater the need of the demand, it is considered to start these Courses.

- Course No. 1: B.Sc. Forensic Science
- Course No. 2: B.Sc. in Respiratory Care
- Course No. 3: Technology, Diploma in Emergency Medicine.

The Decisions were made and was approved by the BOS as suggested from the Academic Year 2018-19.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Laveena D'Souza, Member, Board of Studies.

Dr. Ravi Bhaskar,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Sciences.

Members present:

Dr. Ravi Bhaskar

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Dr. Sukesh

Dr. Vishrutha K V

Ms. Haritha Chandran

Mr. Binoy K Kuriakose

Mr. Anson Jose

Ms. Alphonsa

Dr. Sathyajith Karanth

Dr. Vishnu Prabhu

Mrs. Anitha D'Souza

Ms. Laveena D'Souza

Dr. Ravindran

Ms. Swathi D

Mr. Devaseelan S